

COVID-19 vaccines are a key element for decreasing the number of new infections, minimizing the likelihood of severe infections, and slowing down the pandemic. Racial and ethnic minorities have not only been disproportionately affected by the pandemic in terms of economic impact and mortality but also in terms of rate and speed of vaccination. This study aims to investigate: (1) the prevalence of COVID-19 vaccine uptake and COVID-19 Vaccine hesitancy in Delaware's underserved communities; and (2) factors (demographic, socioeconomic characteristics, & COVID-19 related behaviors) associated with vaccine hesitancy.

WHERE

Delaware, USA

WHEN

Data were collected from March 4, 2021 to May 25, 2021.

WHO

The study included 293 participants (age >18) from Delaware's most underserved communities.

THE POPULATION

We defined underserved communities as areas, geographically indicated by census tract, experiencing high rates of poverty, unemployment, and health disparities.

It should be noted that the sample of this study (n = 293) includes individuals recruited between the dates of March 4, 2021 to May 25, 2021. The study does not include participants recruited from May 26 to October 30. Therefore, the present study only represents about one-third of the total sample recruited for the project, which will be analyzed in future publications.

The Sample

Seventy-three percent of the participants identified as Black.

KEY FINDINGS

- A considerable proportion of participants were categorized as vaccine hesitant in our study sample (60%).

- Being Black increased the likelihood of vaccine hesitancy for the COVID-19 vaccine**, which is consistent with prior studies on vaccine hesitancy.

- Having been tested for COVID in the past decreased the odds of vaccine hesitancy.

MEASURES AND OBSERVATIONS

- Average age: **44.36 (SD=14.55)**
- 64%** high school and lower and **41%** employed
- 45%** family income in 2020 **less than \$20,000**
- 65%** have tested for COVID
- 30%** received one dose of the COVID vaccine compared to **53%** for all Delawareans at that time
- 60%** vaccine hesitant (Respondents who chose the answer "I do not want to get vaccinated," "Prefer not to answer," and "Don't know" were coded as vaccine hesitant, consistent with prior research)

CONCLUSIONS

- Our study represents a critical first step in understanding the determinants driving COVID vaccine uptake and hesitancy. **Identifying key factors and causes for vaccine hesitancy may help in establishing novel strategies that counteract low vaccination rates in underserved communities.**
- It may be beneficial for government and public health services to reach out to vulnerable communities and spread awareness about the safety, effectiveness, and importance of getting vaccinated for COVID-19.

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To read the published research article, radx-up.org.

A Research Collaboration with

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